

Supplementary figure S3: Allele frequency plots

These allele frequency plots were generated for the 7 strains not included in the 1,011 paper by Peter *et al.* and were used to identify clear aneuploidies by manual visual inspection. For each plot we specify the aneuploidies called.

YMD1864

Aneuploidies observed: +1*9

YMD1870

Aneuploidies observed: -1*1

YMD1871

Aneuploidies observed: None

YMD1873

Aneuploidies observed: -1*10

YMD1950

Aneuploidies observed: None

YMD1981

Aneuploidies observed: -1*5;-1*10;-1*12;-1*14

YMD4285

Aneuploidies observed: None